

Methane as a Gasocrine Signal: Perspectives on Potential Methane Protogasoreceptors

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Running title: Methane as a Gasocrine Signal

Keywords: methane, ammonia monooxygenase, AMO, gasocrine signaling, gasoreceptor, protogasoreceptor, riboceptors, gasocrinology, climate change

In the emerging field of gasocrinology, several important questions remain unanswered (1–4). If there are gasoreceptors for nitric oxide or ethylene, then there must be potential gasoreceptors for all naturally generated gases produced by organisms or the environment. Earlier, I had suggested that proteins such as vertebrate hemoglobin should be considered as protogasoreceptors for dioxygen and carbon monoxide in a proto-component signal transduction systems (5, 6). This is an evolutionarily older form of gasoreceptors compared to those functioning in one-component signal transduction systems. This also opened up the potential candidates for hydrogen cyanide protogasoreceptors, namely *Campylobacter jejuni* truncated hemoglobin P (Cj-trHbP) and *A Armoracia rusticana* Peroxidase C1A (PRXC1A), also known as horseradish peroxidase or ferropoxidase) (7).

In an earlier preprint, before the concept of protogasoreceptors emerged, I proposed that molecular methane, could potentially be sensed via F430 (nickel hydrocorphinoid)-based gasoreceptors, or indirectly via methanol-sensing receptors (8, 9). Although I initially thought the majority of the gasoreceptors could be metalloproteins, I considered the possibility that some gasoreceptors could bind gases without metal cofactors (3, 10). This is further exemplified by the fact that N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) receptor exhibits duality as a gasoreceptor by sensing xenon and nitrous oxide (11).

However, given my recent proposal of the concept of protogasoreceptors in the proto-component signal transduction system, it is difficult not to speculate about potential molecular methane-sensing protogasoreceptors. This is especially true given the role of methane in planetary temperature homeostasis via the global biogeochemical nitrogen cycles, as well as in the subfields of planetary and microbial gasocrinology (12–14). Candidate methane protogasoreceptors include the ammonia monooxygenase (AMO) in the archaeal species *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus franklandus* C13 and the bacterial species *Nitrosococcus oceani* (15, 16). Apart from methane, ammonia monooxygenase enzymes atleast in *N. franklandus* C13 seems to a candidate for methanol protogasoreceptor. Nevertheless, further biochemical and structural studies, as well as *in vivo* studies using strains and purified wild-type versus mutant proteins, are necessary to definitely prove or disprove the role of ammonia monooxygenases as protogasoreceptors for methane (17, 18).

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